

Performance aware algorithm design for elastic resource workflow management of cluster consolidation to handle enterprise big data

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 21, 2023

Revised Jan 31, 2024

Accepted Mar 9, 2024

Keywords:

Big data

Elasticity

Heterogeneous workflows

Multi cloud computing

Resource provisioning

ABSTRACT

Integration and deployment of big data and business analytics application with cloud computing are more attractive as a service and are trending practice. This hybrid workflow is rapidly increasing and will trigger a revolution for enterprise data handling, information retrieval and computing. This paper presents hybrid workflow management framework for big data and multi cloud computing systems in a two-step approach. Linear optimization-based resource assessment algorithm is planned in the first step. Cluster oriented elastic resource allocation and workflow management techniques are concentrated in the second step. This paper also focus on performance evaluation parameters includes execution time, through put with multi task work flow optimization model. The proposed framework is efficiently managed the implementation of hybrid workflows by finetuning the evaluation attributes and provides improvement in terms of response time an average of 6%.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Voluminous data processing and pre-processing [1] is required for big data applications has become a major challenge in several incipient domains including scientific, space research, gaming [2], astronomy [3] and healthcare [4]. The need for real data analytics is recognized by the companies like banks are focused on detection of frauds in based on analysing transactional data and smart cities [5] by analysing data from various data sources includes traffic cameras, social media, remote sensing data [6], and global positioning system (GPS) data. For enterprises the cloud based bigdata applications [7] provides business intelligence [8], business strategy adoption and strategies for customer retention. Graphical processing unit (GPUs), tera bytes of storage, datacentres and high speed inter connections are demanded for deployment of hybrid cloud and big data applications. Hence organizations select the cloud computing as fundamental resource provisioning platform [9] to their big data applications. Although each piece of technology has value on its own, many businesses are attempting to integrate them to profit from security and on-demand services. Cloud computing is preferred technology for enterprises to maintain their transactions on demand, reliable deployment of big data in cloud. With the help of cloud computing [10], enterprises can perform better data analysis from the massive amounts of structured and unstructured data [11] in their data processing. This feature of the cloud is origin for the migration of cloud computing across numerous industries and enterprises. Multi cloud computing systems are

beneficial for enterprises to implement when integrated to the large-scale big data resources that organizations have used before. Cloud computing also provides platform enables companies to integrate data from numerous different heterogeneous sources with different data formats and can produce better visualization of results with a more consistent performance [12] to facilitate decision making.

In multi cloud environment cooperative virtual machine [13] form as cluster as processing streams with nearby resources and form as middleware layer to backing cloud services. Clusters has a substantial role in dealing out massive data and only uploads processed data to clouds in multi cloud computing systems for improvement in service availability. Hybrid workflow management require the development of well-organized resource provisioning and forecast techniques which coordinate the execution of hybrid workflows [14] on various clusters.

2. RELATED WORK

Saovapakhiran *et al.* [15] focus on coordination and controlling of clusters in multi cloud environment. The authors concentrate on quality of service (QoS) parameters, how to optimize these parameters during integration of clusters to provide cloud services. Latency based stream processing [16] for computational oriented work flow scheduling is demonstrated by Udoh and Kotonya [17]. The author described the procedure for data aggregation, network synchronization and model prediction of clusters in big data applications. Mastroianni *et al.* [18] illustrated significance of elastic state, dynamic virtual machines consolidation and job scheduling in bigdata framework. Shi and Chen [19] illustrates cost time optimization algorithm for deadline and budget distribution among clusters. The scheduling of tasks is carried out with parent and child groups depending on service request.

3. METHODOLOGY

The cluster cloud model is suitable for hybrid task execution paths, because the watercourse tasks with latency sensitivity [20] can benefit from the availability of resources, whereas batch tasks with hefty workloads can be handled at powerful computation nodes in the multi cloud. Generally, hybrid workflow framework includes three layers namely physical layer, cluster layer and application layer. Physical layer contains servers, internet of things (IoT) sensors that provides fundamental resources for multi cloud infrastructure and storage that handles computational intense applications [21] includes business intelligence, complex visualization [22], and data analytics [23]. Cluster layer facilitates data communication between workflow tasks through hybrid resource scheduling algorithm for multi cloud and big data environment. Application layer provides interaction layer for users and is responsible for collecting information and performing operations in order to provide service.

Workflow management is required to estimate resource allocation for workflows based on quality attributes to choose efficient virtual machines for task execution with the help of selected scheduling algorithm [24]. In proposed work hybrid workflow is a combination of stream and batch tasks. The start and end tasks are fake tasks and not considered for hybrid workflow execution. The main aim of hybrid workflow management is to provide best cluster-based task execution framework to provide service with minimum execution time as in Figure 1.

Hybrid workflow scheduling management allows seamless cooperation between clusters to select execution path based on quality parameters. The resource assessment [25] for the cluster is the optimized workflow configuration that is combination of execution time and number of clusters. In the proposed work a cluster can be number of virtual machines as a single core. After resource assessment allocation and scheduling to tasks of each of a cluster is carried out in the multi cloud environment. Each cluster need to consider execution time (T) and cost (C) and need to achieve as (1).

$$\text{Min}(T, C) \tag{1}$$

Workflow configuration is carried out with cluster request arrival rate and minimum execution time with a smaller number of resources (section-1), prioritize the cluster based on section-1 attributes then assign cluster to the path with the help of cluster-oriented hybrid workflow management algorithm. This approach can enhance the efficiency and accuracy of data processing and analysis in scenarios where data exhibits natural clusters or groups with different characteristics.

Algorithm: Cluster oriented hybrid workflow management

Input: Group of Clusters (G) and Available Computational Resources (D)

Procedure COHWM (G, D)

 Initialize P is set of Paths: P = { }

 Findexecutionpaths(G)

 while clusters do

```

Set cluster to path
Broadcast message to all clusters
while cluster proposal arrives do
    Collect proposal from clusters
    Prioritize clusters
end while
Broadcast message for cluster allocation
while clusters parameter arrives do
    Collect parameter message from cluster
end while
while cluster disagree proposal do
    for all cloud users do
        Build new cluster
    end for
end while
end while
End Procedure
    
```


Figure 1. Hybrid workflow scheduling

4. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

A cluster-oriented hybrid workflow algorithm is a type of algorithm that combines elements from different workflow and clustering techniques to solve specific problems efficiently. This algorithm is often used in data analysis, machine learning, and optimization tasks. The multi-cloud and big data environment with hybrid workflow is deployed with Peacock [26] as a self-governing component with Java [27] Spark [28] add-ins composed with Scala [29]. The proposed work utilised Sparrow [30] combined with code from Eagle [31] to serve the big data enterprise trials as in Figure 2 and the characteristics of the workload are described in Table 1.

Figure 2. Proposed system environment

Table 1. Workload characteristics

Workloads	Taskset count	Task count	Average task duration
Google	5,04,482	17,80,043	68
Yahoo	29,262	9,92,497	119
Cloudera	21,033	5,76,097	102

To assess average cluster workloads, the task influx time is distributed with a poisson process and a mean task arrival time is estimated based on a predictable average workload percentage, mean task execution time, and mean number of tasks per cluster. Due to heterogeneous tasks, the workload also becomes heterogeneous during the execution of tasks, and the average execution time is 6% and the execution time is illustrated in Figure 3. The proposed work contains 30%, 40%, and 70% light cluster workloads and 100%, 150%, and 200% heavy cluster workloads. The cumulative distribution of task completion for 10,000 clusters is described in Figure 4, (Figure 4(a) Google 300%) illustrates the integrated distribution of tasks termination for 10000 clusters and (Figure 4(b) Google-50%) demonstrates that, with a 50% load, sparrow can only do 2.2% of jobs in less than 100 seconds, compared to 21.6% for Peacock in the same amount of time. As seen in Figure 4(c) Google-300%, when under 300% load, Sparrow completes 0.3% of tasks in less than 100 seconds, compared to 31.8% for Peacock. The Yahoo! trace has longer task durations, so we check for 1000 seconds. At 50% load in Figure 4(d) Yahoo-50%, the percentages for Sparrow and Peacock are in order of 5% and 23.5% but with Cloudera the 300% and 50% comparison is shown in Figure 4(e) Cloudera 300% and Figure 4(f) Cloudera 50% respectively. The workload distribution of a cluster is demonstrated in Figure 5.

Figure 3. Execution time

Figure 4. Integrated distribution of tasks termination for 10000 clusters, (a) Google-300%, (b) Google-50%, (c) Yahoo-300%, (d) Yahoo-50%, (e) Cloudera-300%, and (f) Cloudera-50%

Figure 5. Workload of clusters

5. CONCLUSION

Generally, the big data frameworks split jobs into various parallel processing tasks that are executed with small partition of data with low latency. Such frameworks depend on distributed schedulers to handle the attached overhead. The existing algorithms not efficiently performed during workload variations with heterogeneous jobs. The hybrid workflow management algorithm considers heterogeneous jobs both stream and batch provide improvement in terms of execution time an average of 6%.

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